

Polarographic Behaviour of Some Potential Antidiabetic 4-Arylhydrazono-N¹-Hippuryl-3-Methyl-2-Pyrazolin-5-ones

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Polarographic studies of some 4-arylhydrazono-N¹-hippuryl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones have been carried out in B.R. buffer in the pH range 2.0-12.0. All the compounds gave single, well defined, irreversible, diffusion-controlled reduction wave whose $E_{1/2}$ value is pH-dependent but i_d remains constant throughout the entire pH range. The $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards negative potentials with increase in pH, thereby showing that protonation precedes reduction. A linear correlation is observed between the $E_{1/2}$ values and the Hammett substituent constants indicating that substituents appreciably affect the reduction of -NH-N=C- group by polar and mesomeric effects. The effect of the double layer structure on the $E_{1/2}$ has also been studied.

PYRAZOLES and pyrazolin-5-ones possess interesting antidiabetic¹⁻³ or antineoplastic⁴ activity. In view of the fact that the physiological activity of a molecule is closely related to its redox behaviour⁵ in the cell membrane, it was considered worthwhile to study the redox behaviour of some potential antidiabetic, 4-arylhydrazono-N¹-hippuryl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (I) at d.m.e.

The objective of investigating the electrochemical behaviour of the present biologically important arylazopyrazoles was based on the dependence of characteristic potential i.e. half-wave potential on electron density and other factors which in turn are correlated to biological, clinical, physical and chemical property and activity^{5,6}. As a simple relationship exists between structure, half-wave potential and reactivity, a better understanding of the effect of structure on the redox behaviour of these compounds can be obtained⁷. The present paper summarises the electrochemical behaviour of some hippurylpyrazoles (I) with special reference to the effect of substituents and surfactants on their redox mechanism.

Experimental

The compounds(1-15) were prepared by the method described in literature⁴. Stock solutions of all the compounds were prepared in distilled DMF (AnalaR). Britton-Robinson buffers⁸ in the pH range 2.0-12.0 were prepared as usual.

An ELICO DC recording polarograph, Model CL-25 was used. The capillary characteristics were

1.75 mg^{2/3}sec^{-1/2}. SCE was used as the reference electrode.

For recording polarograms at 30.0±0.1°, stock solution (1 ml, 1.0×10⁻³M) of compound, 1M KCl (1 ml), DMF (2 ml) (the minimum amount necessary to keep the compounds in solutions), gelatin (0.5 ml) and buffer (5.5 ml) were mixed and a stream of pure nitrogen gas passed for about 15 min to ensure complete deaeration.

The number of electrons involved in the reduction process was calculated by millicoulometry⁹ using CdSO₄ as the reference solution. The controlled potential electrolysis was carried out at a potential corresponding to the plateau of the wave. After complete electrolysis (10 hr) the catholyte was subjected to product analysis. The uv spectra of the solution during electrolysis were recorded at different time intervals on a UV-VIS Carl-Zeiss recording spectrophotometer. The temperature coefficient was calculated by Nejedly's method¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

The compounds(1-15) listed in Table 1 gave a single 4e reduction wave in B.R. buffer of pH range 2.0-12.0. The nature of the waves was diffusion-controlled as shown by the linear dependence of limiting current on \sqrt{t} and the concentration of the depolarizer. The constancy of wave height in the pH range studied, together with the fact that di/dt had a very low value of temperature coefficient further confirmed that the reduction waves were fully diffusion-controlled. The wave characteristics are shown in Table 1.

The half-wave potentials of these compounds were found to be dependent on pH and shifted towards more negative potential with increase in pH. The plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH were linear with slopes in the range 0.073 to 0.080 upto pH 8.6,

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME 4-ARYLHYDRAZONO-N¹-HIPPIRYL-3-METHYL-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONES AT pH 6.8 ; CONC. = 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M

Compd. No.	R	-E _{1/2} V	i _d μA	ΔE _{1/2} V	dE _{1/2} / d pH ; V / pH	I × 10 ⁻³	αn	p
1.	H	0.76	1.75	0.00	0.080	0.85	0.64	0.92
2.	2-Cl	0.67	1.90	0.09	0.076	0.93	0.67	0.96
3.	3-Cl	0.72	1.75	0.06	0.076	0.85	0.64	0.96
4.	4-Cl	0.74	1.75	0.08	0.80	0.85	0.63	1.02
5.	2-OCH ₃	0.74	1.85	0.02	0.082	0.90	0.67	1.02
6.	4-OCH ₃	0.81	1.75	0.05	0.070	0.85	0.63	0.96
7.	2-CH ₃	0.71	1.90	0.04	0.073	0.93	0.63	0.96
8.	3-CH ₃	0.76	1.85	0.00	0.070	0.90	0.64	0.92
9.	4-CH ₃	0.78	1.85	0.02	0.076	0.90	0.67	1.02
10.	2-Br	0.68	1.90	0.08	0.080	0.93	0.67	0.96
11.	4-Br	0.72	1.75	0.04	0.076	0.85	0.63	0.96
12.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	0.76	1.75	0.00	0.073	0.85	0.67	1.02
13.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	0.80	1.80	0.04	0.074	0.88	0.64	1.02
14.	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	0.76	1.85	0.00	0.076	0.90	0.64	0.92
15.	3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	0.74	1.85	0.02	0.076	0.90	0.64	1.02

thereafter, there was a small change in E_{1/2} and the value of the slope was significantly small (Fig. 1). The irreversible nature of the waves was confirmed by log plots. The fact that E_{1/2} shifted towards more negative potential with increasing concentration of depolarizer further points towards the irreversible nature¹¹ of the waves. The values of αn and p were determined^{11,12} as usual and are given in Table 1.

Since the half-wave potentials of these pyrazolines were pH-dependent and the limiting current pH-independent upto pH 8.6, it was concluded that both acidic and basic forms of the compounds reached the electrode surface and were electroactive. The proton transfer reaction precedes the electrode process in such cases. Out of the two general sequences¹³ for the proton and electron addition viz., H⁺,e,H⁺,e and H⁺,e,e,H⁺, the former sequence is more probable for these compounds in the light of their structural genesis. After the uptake of a proton and one electron the radical (III) would accept a proton to form a protonated radical (IV) which after taking one electron gets cleaved at the nitrogen bond with the formation of aniline. The imine(V) formed gets further protonated and reduced.

Alternatively, the radical (III) could also combine with an electron instead of proton but this possibility is ruled out by the fact that such a reduction would involve only 2-electrons whereas polarographic data clearly indicate 4-electron transfer reaction at the d.m.e.

These mechanistic steps find support from the increase of E_{1/2} with pH as protons are consumed in the reduction. As the equilibrium tends towards the unprotonated form, the E_{1/2} tends to become constant. Fig. 1 shows that above pH 8.6, the shift in E_{1/2} with pH towards negative potentials is not so marked as in the acidic pH range. In fact, E_{1/2} becomes practically constant. This constancy in E_{1/2} may be due to the fact that both the acidic and basic forms of the depolarizer are electroactive but in the pH range where the protonation rate decreases, their half-wave potentials are so close to each other that the waves merge¹³.

The half-wave potentials in the pH region defined by $(pK_1+1) < pH < (pK_1-1)$ are shifted towards more negative values. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ against pH in this region is linear and corresponds to equation

$$E_{1/2} = C - \frac{RT}{\alpha nF} \ln K_1 + \frac{RT}{\alpha nF} \ln [H^+]$$

At $pH > (pK_1+1)$ the half-wave potential of the acidic form is pH -independent and practically equal to the half-wave potential of the basic form.

$$(E_{1/2})_{HA} = C - \frac{RT}{2\alpha nF} \ln K_1 - \frac{RT}{\alpha nF} \ln 0.886/K_1 t_1 - \frac{RT}{\alpha nF} \ln K_1 \approx (E_{1/2})_A$$

The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH is composed of two linear segments intersecting each other (Fig. 1) and the pH at the point of intersection of its two linear parts is approximately equal to pK_1 .

Fig. 1. Plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH for some typical 4-arylhydrazono- N^1 -hippuryl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones.

Due to an acid-base equilibrium between the two structural forms of the compounds H^+ ($-N=N- \rightleftharpoons -NH^+=N-$), the wave height remains pH -independent as long as the formation of the acidic form from the basic form is fast enough. As the pH increases and the rate of the protonation decreases, the wave height also decreases.

When the depolarizer solution was tested after controlled potential electrolysis, it gave the dye test thereby showing that at least one of the reduction products is an aromatic amine. UV spectra of the solution during electrolysis were recorded at different time intervals. λ_{max} at 380 nm due to $-NH-N=C-$ grouping showed a decrease in the peak height after each interval of time and finally the wave disappeared, confirming the above reduction mechanism.

Effect of substituents :

The effect of substituents on the ease of reduction was determined quantitatively by applying Hammett equation. Since the values of α (transfer coefficient) and $dE_{1/2}/dpH$ were the same for all these compounds, Hammett equation could be applied successfully⁷. When $E_{1/2}$ of these compounds were plotted against Hammett substituent

constants (σ), a linear relationship was obtained (Fig. 2). It will be observed that the values for *meta* and *para* derivatives fit in the straight line while the *ortho* derivatives, viz., 2-chloro, 2-methoxy, 2-methyl, 2-bromo, 2-ethoxy and 2,3-dimethyl deviate significantly from the linear plot.

Fig. 2. Plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs σ for 4-arylhydrazono- N^1 -hippuryl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones at pH 6.8.

From the plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs σ , the specific reaction constant (ρ) was found to be 0.13 V. Its positive sign indicated the nucleophilic nature of the electrode process¹⁴. The observed linear relationship of $E_{1/2}$ vs σ indicates that the substituents appreciably affected the reduction of hydrazono group by polar and mesomeric effects through the benzene ring.

Effect of ionic strength :

The effect of the double layer structure on the $E_{1/2}$ of a process preceded by the protonation is given by equation (1)¹⁵.

$$\Delta E_{1/2} \approx \Delta \psi_1 \left(\frac{\alpha n_a - Z}{\alpha n_a} - \frac{\partial E_{1/2} \cdot F}{\partial pH \cdot 2.30RT} \right) \dots (1)$$

where ψ_1 is the variation in the double layer potential, α the transfer coefficient, n_a the number of electrons transferred in the rate determining step and Z the charge of the particle being discharged. Undoubtedly, a marked effect of change in ionic strength on $E_{1/2}$ should be observed in case where the depolarizer is in the ionic form. No such effect should be observed when it is in the non-ionic form i.e. when $Z=0$. Since the second term in the bracket of eq. (1) is nearly 1 and $Z=0$, $E_{1/2}$ will be almost independent of ψ_1 or of ionic strength. This was verified by carrying out experiments with varying concentration of KCl (0.01 M and 0.25 M). The values of $dE_{1/2}/dpH$ thus obtained fall in the range 0.070-0.080 V/pH and $E_{1/2}$ and i_d remained unaffected by the change in concentration of the supporting electrolyte.

Effect of surfactants :

Ionic (cationic and anionic) as well as non-ionic surfactants suppressed the maxima completely. No

appreciable change in i_d and $E_{1/2}$ or shape of the wave was observed with the cationic (cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide, cetylpyridinium bromide) and anionic (alkylaryl sulphonates) surfactants in the acidic as well as in the alkaline pH range. However, on adding non-ionic surfactants besides the suppression of the maxima, other changes in polarographic wave were also found to occur at higher pH. On addition of increasing amount of non-ionic surfactant after the maximum suppression point (MSP) the $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative potential.

Such shift indicates that the non-ionic surfactants are specifically adsorbed at the mercury surface through hydrogen bond formation between the oriented solvent (water) molecules in the Inner Helmholtz Plane (IHP) and the ether oxygen of the polyoxyethylene chain. In this connection it is worthwhile pointing out that ionic surfactants give fairly highly hydrated micelles in comparison to non-ionic surfactants and, therefore, the chances of the former reaching the IHP are much less than the latter. This may be one of the reasons why only the non-ionic surfactant affect markedly the polarographic reduction of the compounds under discussion while no such effect is observed either with cationic or anionic surfactants.

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